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I-MOVE-COVID-19 Network

Multidisciplinary European network for research, prevention and control of the COVID-19 pandemic

COVID-19 European primary care surveillance: Second surveillance bulletin

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Version history

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v2	02/24/2021	Nivel	Draft version circulated among partners
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Abbreviations

ARI	Acute respiratory infection
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
EEA	European Economic Area
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EU	European Union
GP	General Practitioner
ILI	Influenza-like illness
I-MOVE	Influenza – Monitoring Vaccine Effectiveness in Europe
RCGP RSC	Royal College of General Practitioners Research and Surveillance Centre
SARS-CoV-2	Severe acute respiratory syndrome – coronavirus 2
VE	Vaccine effectiveness

1. Summary

1.1. Background

This surveillance report summarises the information from the nine I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care surveillance networks to monitor the COVID-19 pandemic in seven European countries. The I-MOVE-COVID-19 surveillance in primary care aims to reinforce and complement the COVID-19 epidemiological data in the EU/EEA and the UK, compiled and reported by ECDC. Throughout this surveillance report, persons who tested positive for SARS-CoV-2 virus in primary care are referred to as “COVID-19 cases”.

This second surveillance report encompasses the start of the pandemic in March 2020 until January 2021. The first semester of 2020 ranges from March to June and will be referred to as ‘first reporting period’, the second semester ranges from July 2020 to January 2021 and is referred to as ‘second reporting period’.

Data for the I-MOVE-COVID-19 surveillance in primary care is collected following a generic protocol. However, there are differences between networks in the data collected, due to differences in health care systems or coding of data.

1.2. Key findings

- All participating study sites provided data for COVID-19 surveillance in primary care.
- A total of 35,871 COVID-19 cases were reported by nine participating networks in the period March 2020 – January 2021. Due to their sampling method, the Spanish region of Navarra reported the majority of cases.
- The majority of cases were reported in the age band 25 to 49 years, with a shift to younger age groups in the period July 2020 – January 2021 compared with March – June 2020.
- In March to June 2020 slightly more females were reported than in July 2020 – January 2021 (56% versus 52%).
- In the youngest age groups of 0 to 14 years, the majority of cases was male (53%), in all other age groups the majority of cases was female.
- The most frequently reported symptom in the period March – June 2020 was cough (82%), followed by fever (71%). The least often reported symptom was vomiting (10%). In the period July 2020 – January 2021, the most often reported symptoms were the same, however percentages of cases for whom the symptoms was reported were lower: cough 69%, fever 53%, and vomiting 4%.
- Although most reported symptoms did not differ according to age group, within age groups percentages of reported symptoms did differ. For instance whereas cough was reported for 58% of cases in the age band 0 – 24 years, in the age group 65 – 79 years 77% reported cough.
- The median time between onset of symptoms and date of testing was 1 day (IQR 0-4). The median time between onset and testing decreased over time.
- Any chronic condition was reported for 36% of the cases of 25 years and older, with the majority of cases in the oldest age groups reporting any condition: 64% among cases of 65 – 79 years and

73% among cases of 80 years and older. The most often reported chronic condition was heart disease among the age group of 80 years and older (49%), followed by diabetes among age group 80 years and older (24%).

- Chronic conditions were more often reported for males compared with females: for any chronic condition 39% for males versus 35% for females. Heart disease was reported for 16% of the males versus 11% of the females, diabetes for 12% of males and 8% of the females.
- The majority of COVID-19 cases of 15 years and older never smoked. Percentages varied according to period of reporting, with 64% never smoked in March – June 2020 and 80% never smoked in July 2020 – January 2021.
- Seasonal influenza vaccination was reported for 30% of COVID-19 cases aged 25 years and older. Among the age groups with an indication for vaccination, the vaccination rate was higher (37 – 42%)
- A selection of specimens from COVID-19 positive patients were used for virus isolation and sequencing of viruses. The B.1 lineage was observed in the majority of specimens in the period 10 March to 30 June 2020. In the period 1 July – 31 December 2020 the dominant lineage was B.1.177.

2. Enhanced COVID-19 surveillance

2.1. Description of participating networks

Table 1 briefly describes participating networks and their contribution of data to this report. Note that the time period for which data were submitted does not necessarily reflect the total duration of the data collection, nor the epidemic in that country. In many countries, dedicated COVID-19 testing hubs were established in 2020, impacting on the data collection for virological surveillance carried out by sentinel GPs prior to the COVID-19 pandemic. In some countries, new sentinel GP data collection systems were established.

Table 1. Description of participating I-MOVE primary care COVID-19 surveillance networks, March 2020 to January 2021

Network (country)	Coverage or number of participating GP practices	First week of data included*	Last week of data included
RCGP RSC (England)	237 practices	week 39, 2020	week 4, 2021
Réseau Sentinelles (France)	~ 350 practices	week 12, 2020	week 4, 2021
Irish GP influenza sentinel surveillance system (Ireland)	60	week 47, 2020	week 4, 2021
Navarra (Spain)	53	week 8, 2020	week 4, 2021
Nivel Primary Care Database - Sentinel Practices (Netherlands)	~ 40 practices	week 10, 2020	week 4, 2021
Rede Médicos-Sentinela (Portugal)	8 COVID-19 testing centers	week 47, 2020	week 4, 2021
NHS community pathways, primarily comprising COVID-19 community assessment centres and triage hubs (Scotland)	~ 14 NHS Boards across Scotland	week 16, 2020	week 4, 2021
Spanish Sentinel Surveillance System of Acute Respiratory Infections (Spain)	53 GPs and 27 paediatricians in two regions	week 44, 2020	week 4, 2021
Sentinelövervakning /Sentinel Surveillance Network (Sweden)	~ 90 practices	week 10, 2020	week 4, 2021

* Week numbers reflect the period of data included in this surveillance report.

England (EN) – Data is collected from the sentinel GP practices participating in the RCGP RSC network. For surveillance purposes, data were selected from patients with symptoms consulting their GP with a diagnosis of "COVID-19", "COVID-19 illness" or "Main symptom" (ie. presenting with fever, cough, loss of sense of smell, or loss of sense of taste) and tested for positive for SARS-CoV-2. We excluded records of subsequent positive SARS-CoV-2 tests.

France (FR) – Data is collected from ARI patients consulting in primary care with GPs participating in the Sentinelles network. A sample of these ARI patients is tested for SARS-CoV-2, influenza and other respiratory viruses. The data collection has been adapted since week 21, 2020, with more information on symptoms and comorbidity, but no longer information on influenza vaccination or influenza virus co-infection. Symptoms are reported as free text have not yet been included in the analyses.

Ireland (IE) – At the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, virological surveillance with the Irish sentinel GP network was disrupted, when face to face GP consultations were stopped. All patients with COVID-19 like symptoms are advised to phone their GP. Virological surveillance with the sentinel GP network was re-established in November 2020, including all COVID-19 phone consultations to the sentinel GP network. Surveillance of COVID-19 with the Irish sentinel GP network was integrated into the national COVID-19 referral pathway, with all patients with COVID-19 symptoms referred to COVID-19 community testing centres for swabbing. Sentinel GP specimens are identified and routed directly to the National Virus Reference Laboratory for SARS-CoV-2 testing. Data reported includes all patients meeting the Irish COVID-19 case definition and consulting (via phone) a sentinel GP in Ireland. Sentinel GP patients without COVID-19 symptoms were excluded.

Navarra (NA) – The data is collected from ARI patients in primary care from all the Navarra population. Since week 20 (2020), all outpatients with COVID-19 symptoms have been tested. Healthcare workers and nursing home residents were excluded from the dataset used for this surveillance report.

Netherlands (NL) – The routine influenza surveillance system in sentinel primary care practices was continued, with additional testing for SARS-CoV-2 of all samples in addition to influenza and other respiratory viruses. From 1 June 2020, every citizen with any respiratory symptom can request a diagnostic (PCR) test at dedicated testing centres. Therefore the number of ILI/ARI patients in primary care eligible for swabbing has decreased considerably and may not be representative for all persons suspected of COVID-19.

Portugal (PT) – A new sentinel surveillance system was set up, based on a selection of ARI cases among patients visiting primary care centres with respiratory symptoms. Cases were selected using a systematic sampling method (five cases/week per centre). Laboratory data for SARS-CoV-2 and influenza were available for all cases. Information on underlying chronic diseases and medication may become available through data linkage at a later stage.

Scotland (SC) - The routine GP Sentinel Swabbing Scheme for influenza was stepped down as consultations stopped at practice level. Instead, dedicated NHS COVID-19 triage hubs and community assessment centres were set up across Scotland. From June 2020, patients who are

unwell in the community with symptoms compatible with COVID-19 are referred for NHS clinical assessment, either in person or over the telephone. These patients are offered a diagnostic COVID-19 test and asked to provide information about themselves to Public Health Scotland (self-reported by the patient or supplied by the clinical assessment centre) for COVID-19 surveillance purposes. Those patients for whom a test result and enhanced surveillance data are available are included in the community surveillance dataset.

Spain (ES) – The well-consolidated Spanish Influenza Sentinel Surveillance System in primary care was disrupted with the emergence of COVID-19 pandemic, just when the influenza season 2019-20 was almost finishing in Spain. Because of surveillance work since June 2020, a new Spanish Sentinel Surveillance System of Acute Respiratory Infections in Primary Care has been implemented in Spain. For the purpose of this report, data from two Spanish regions are included, although other regions are already working and will become participant in a near future. Data from all ARI cases consulting sentinel primary care are collected with information on sex, age, symptoms and presumption of ILI. Respiratory swabs are systematically taken from the first two-five ARI patients per week. From those swabbed patients, information on chronic diseases, virological and influenza and COVID-19 vaccination is collected. Improving completeness of variables is ongoing.

Sweden (SE) – Data and samples for both enhanced and aggregated surveillance are collected on all patients with influenza-like illness (ILI) and acute respiratory infection (ARI) who consult a sentinel physician. The existing influenza sentinel surveillance system was expanded in week 10 of 2020 to include COVID-19. While the influenza sentinel surveillance phased out in week 16 of 2020, the COVID-19 sentinel surveillance remained active throughout 2020. During the first wave in 2020, sentinel practices had exclusive access to COVID-19 testing for health workers and those with moderate or severe illness. This led to increased numbers attending for consultation with a three-fold increase in sentinel samples taken. Generalised access to testing from June 2020 led to major declines in participating practices. Efforts are now ongoing to encourage GPs to participate given access to both influenza and COVID-19 testing and financial reimbursement for the first five swabs taken per week. Specific symptoms were not collected during the reporting period 2019/2020, but will be going forward. The 2020/2021 season of the influenza sentinel surveillance started in week 40 2020 and will end after week 20 2021 for both influenza and COVID-19 testing.

Table 2. Main characteristics of I-MOVE primary care COVID-19 surveillance systems, March 2020 to January 2021

Network (country)	Case definition*	Testing strategy
RCGP RSC (England)	1) ILI or ARI 2) patients with a wider range of symptoms	1) Sentinel testing 2) Population testing
Réseau Sentinelles (France)	ARI	Until week 20, 2020: systematic sample Since week 21, 2020: all patients
Irish GP influenza sentinel surveillance system (Ireland)	ARI or ILI**	All patients meeting the COVID-19 case definition are tested for SARS-CoV-2. All patients meeting the influenza case definition are tested for SARS-CoV-2 and influenza.
Navarra (Spain)	ARI	All outpatients with COVID-19 symptoms
Nivel Primary Care Database - Sentinel Practices (Netherlands)	ILI or ARI	Systematic sample
Rede Médicos-Sentinela (Portugal)	ARI	All patients, but a systematic sample is provided for the I-MOVE-COVID-19 project
NHS COVID-19 community assessment centres and triage hubs (Scotland)	ILI or ARI or altered sense of smell/taste	All patients are tested, but only those for whom enhanced surveillance data are also available are included in the community surveillance programme.
Spanish Sentinel Surveillance System of Acute Respiratory Infections (Spain)	ARI	Systematic sample
Sentinelövervakning /Sentinel Surveillance Network (Sweden)	ILI or ARI	Systematic sample

* ILI = influenza-like illness; ARI = acute respiratory illness

** Irish case definitions: www.hpsc.ie/a-z/respiratory/coronavirus/novelcoronavirus/casedefinitions/covid-19interimcasedefinitionforireland/ (COVID-19) and www.hpsc.ie/a-z/respiratory/influenza/casedefinitions/ (influenza)

Table 3. Site-specific surveillance websites of participating I-MOVE primary care COVID-19 networks, March 2020 to January 2021

Network (country)	URL
RCGP RSC (England)	www.rcgp.org.uk/rsc
Réseau Sentinelles (France)	https://www.sentiweb.fr/france/en/?page=bulletin
Irish GP influenza sentinel surveillance system (Ireland)	www.hpsc.ie
Navarra (Spain)	
Nivel Primary Care Database - Sentinel Practices (Netherlands)	www.nivel.nl/nl/nivel-zorgregistraties-eerste-lijn/actuele-weekcijfers-aandoeningen-waaronder-griep-surveillance
Rede Médicos-Sentinela (Portugal)	www.insa.min-saude.pt/category/informacao-e-cultura-cientifica/publicacoes/atividade-gripal/
NHS COVID-19 community assessment centres and triage hubs (Scotland)	www.hps.scot.nhs.uk/web-resources/container/enhanced-surveillance-of-covid-19-in-scotland-community-surveillance-protocol/
Spanish Sentinel Surveillance System of Acute Respiratory Infections (Spain)	vgripe.isciii.es/inicio.do www.isciii.es/QueHacemos/Servicios/VigilanciaSaludPublicaRENAVE/EnfermedadesTransmisibles/Paginas/Gripe.aspx
Sentinelövervakning /Sentinel Surveillance Network (Sweden)	https://www.folkhalsomyndigheten.se/folkhalsorapportering-statistik/statistik-a-o/sjukdomsstatistik/covid-19-veckorapporter/senaste-covidrapporten/

NOTE:

All figures in this report are based on data reported by I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care networks from March 2020 to January 2021.

The results reported are approved by all partners.

Data have been weighted for differences between study sites, due to sample size and data collection methods, using random effects logistic models with study site as random effect.

In this report, all COVID-19 cases are laboratory confirmed for SARS-CoV-2.

* Week number refers to the week in which the swab specimen was taken. Week numbers range from week 8 – 53 in 2020 to weeks 1 – 4 in 2021.

2.3. Demographic characteristics of COVID-19 cases

The age profile of COVID-19 cases presenting to primary care may be younger as they are generally milder cases compared to hospitalised patients. Older, more severe cases may not be fully represented in this dataset. In Portugal, for example, being 65 years or older is one of the criteria to be referred to a hospital emergency department. In several countries, among others Ireland and the Netherlands, the primary care surveillance systems exclude residents of long term care facilities.

Figure 2. Percentage of COVID-19 cases by age group and by reporting period (pooled data, N=35,867)

Figure 3. Percentage of COVID-19 cases by age group and sex for each reporting period (pooled data*)

* March – June 2020: N=3,543; July 2020 – January 2021: N=32,320

2.4. Symptoms of COVID-19 cases

Results on symptoms are based on data reported by different countries for each symptom, and are reported only if collected in at least two countries. The reporting of symptoms may be related to the definition of patients eligible for I-MOVE-COVID-19 surveillance by protocol. Therefore, asymptomatic cases are not expected.

Figure 4. Symptoms reported by COVID-19 cases, comparison between reporting periods (pooled data*)

A.

B.

* Pooled data differs according to symptom (N in pooled data both reporting periods, countries): fever: n=4,030 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC), malaise: n=2,518 (ES, FR, NL), myalgia: 2,565 (ES, FR, NL, PT), headache: 4,022 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC), coryza: 2,345 (FR, NL, PT), shortness of breath: 3,628 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC), vomiting: 3,897 (ES, FR, PT, SC), diarrhoea: 4,013 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC), fatigue: 3,629 (FR, PT, SC), cough: 4,052 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC).

Figure 5. Symptoms reported by COVID-19 cases by age-group (pooled data*)

A

B

C

* Pooled data differs according to symptom (N in pooled data both reporting periods, countries): fever: n=4,030 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC), malaise: n=2,518 (ES, FR, NL), myalgia: 2,565 (ES, FR, NL, PT), sore throat: 4,013 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC), headache: 4,022 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC), coryza: 2,345 (FR, NL, PT), shortness of breath: 3,628 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC), vomiting: 3,897 (ES, FR, PT, SC), diarrhoea: 4,013 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC), fatigue: 3,629 (FR, PT, SC), cough: 4,052 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC).

Figure 6. Symptoms reported by COVID-19 cases, by sex (pooled data*)

A.

B.

* Pooled data differs according to symptom (N in pooled data both reporting periods, countries): fever: n=4,030 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC), malaise: n=2,518 (ES, FR, NL), myalgia: 2,565 (ES, FR, NL, PT), sore throat: 4,013 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC), headache: 4,022 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC), coryza: 2,345 (FR, NL, PT), shortness of breath: 3,628 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC), vomiting: 3,897 (ES, FR, PT, SC), diarrhoea: 4,013 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC), fatigue: 3,629 (FR, PT, SC), cough: 4,052 (ES, FR, NL, PT, SC).

2.5. Time between onset of symptoms and testing

The median time between onset of symptoms and date of testing was 1 day (IQR 0-4). The median time between onset and testing decreased over time.

Table 4. Number of days between onset of symptoms and swab specimen was taken (pooled data N= 6,228)

	Number of cases	Median	25 th Percentile	75 th Percentile
All COVID-19 cases	6,228	1	0	4
By month				
(2020) March	134	4	2	7
April	141	5	2	9
May	120	4	2	7.5
June	37	5	3	6
July	14	4	2	7
August	39	3	1	6
September	156	3	1	7
October	750	2	0	4
November	871	1	0	4
December	1,461	1	0	4
(2021) January	2,502	1	0	3
By age group				
0 – 4 yrs	108	1	0	3
5 – 14 yrs	211	0	0	3
15 – 24 yrs	527	1	0	3
25 – 49 yrs	2,393	1	0	4
50 – 64 yrs	1,675	2	0	5
65 – 79 yrs	871	3	0	5
80+ yrs	440	2	0	4
By sex				
Female	3,521	1	0	4
Male	2,706	1	0	4

2.6. Co-infections of COVID-19 cases

Co-infections with influenza virus were reported by France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, and Sweden. One co-infection with influenza virus was observed in an elderly person (80+ years) in the Netherlands in week 13, 2020. Data on co-infections with respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), rhinovirus, and enterovirus were provided by the Netherlands only. RSV was observed in two adult persons, in week 11 and 14. Rhinovirus was observed twice in an adult person as well, in week 47 and 50, whereas enterovirus was not observed.

2.7. Referral to hospital of COVID-19 cases

Data regarding referral to hospital was provided by France and Spain. 78 patients were referred (4.5%), of whom one third in the age band 25 – 64 years, 31% in the age-group 65 – 79 years, and 36% in the age-group of 80 years and older.

2.8. Underlying (chronic) conditions of COVID-19 cases

Results on underlying chronic conditions are based on data reported by England, France, Navarra, the Netherlands, Scotland, Spain, and Sweden. Exceptions are cancer and asthma, that were collected only in England, France, and Navarra.

Figure 7. Underlying conditions reported by COVID-19 cases of 25 years and older, by reporting period (pooled data)*

* N=26,965 – 23,244 based on the variable 'presence of any chronic condition for any of the chronic conditions as collected by the country.

Figure 8. Underlying conditions reported by COVID-19 cases, by age group (pooled data*)

* N=26,965 – 23,244 based on the variable ‘presence of any chronic condition’ for any of the chronic conditions as collected by the country.

Figure 9. Underlying conditions reported by COVID-19 cases of 25 years and older, by sex (pooled data*)

* N=26,965 – 23,244 based on the variable ‘presence of any chronic condition’ for any of the chronic conditions as collected by the country.

2.9. Obesity among COVID-19 cases

Information on obesity was collected in England, France, Navarra, the Netherlands, Scotland, and Spain. Obese was defined as a Body Mass Index (BMI) of 30 or higher (FR (from week 17 2020 onwards), NL, and SP) and as BMI of 40 or higher (FR (until week 17 2020), EN, and NA). Obesity was reported for 876 COVID-19 cases (3.5%), most of whom were female (two thirds).

2.10. Smoking status of COVID-19 cases

The results on smoking status are presented for cases aged 15 years or older. A former smoker ceased smoking more than one year ago. Smoking status was collected by France, Navarra, the Netherlands, Scotland, and Spain.

Figure 10. Smoking status of COVID-19 cases aged 15 years or older, by reporting period (pooled data, N=8,223)

Figure 11. Smoking status of COVID-19 cases aged 15 years or older, by sex (pooled data, N=8,223)

2.11. Pregnancy status of COVID-19 cases

Results on pregnancy are restricted to female COVID-19 patients aged between 15 and 45 years. Data regarding pregnancy were provided by France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Scotland, Spain, and Sweden. 21 COVID-19 cases were found to be pregnant (3%).

2.12. Seasonal influenza vaccination status of COVID-19 cases

The result of seasonal influenza status are based on the data collected by all countries. From March to August 2020, vaccination status refers to being vaccinated in 2019, in September 2020 vaccination status may refer to either being vaccinated in 2019 or 2020, and from October 2020 onwards, vaccination status refers to being vaccinated in 2020. Results are presented for cases aged 25 years or older, because immunisation programmes for younger age groups differ between countries.

Figure 12. Seasonal influenza vaccination status of COVID-19 cases, by age and sex (pooled data, N=25,998)

2.13. Health care workers among COVID-19 cases

Data regarding whether a COVID-19 case was a healthcare worker was provided by France, Ireland, Navarra, and Scotland. In France, Ireland and Scotland 118 COVID-19 cases were indicated as healthcare worker (10%).

2.14. Recent travel of COVID-19 cases

Data on recent travel was collected by the Netherlands and Sweden. Five cases were observed who recently travelled.

2.15. Sequence and isolate viruses of respiratory samples from COVID-19 positive cases

A selection of specimens from COVID-19 positive patients in Ireland, the Netherland and Sweden were used for virus isolation and sequencing of viruses . The sequencing results are shared in GISAID. Dedicated bioinformatics pipelines will be used for analysis of viral sequencing data. These data will be provided to WP4 for epidemiological and modelling studies.

Table 5. Characterised viruses of COVID-19 cases, by country

Time period	Lineages	SE		NL		IE		Total ^a	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
10 Mar – 30 Jun 2020	Total SARS-CoV-2	246		65		NA		311	
	Total sequenced	175	71	50	77	NA		225	72
	B.1 ^b	94	54	6	12			100	44
	B.1.177 ^c	0	0	0				0	0
	B.1.1.7	0	0	0				0	0
	B.1.351	0	0	0				0	0
	P.1	0	0	0				0	0
Other lineages ^d	81	46	44	88			125	56	
1 Jul – 31 Dec 2020	Total SARS-CoV-2	46		36		NA		82	
	Total sequenced	32	70	28	78	NA		60	73
	B.1 ^b	0	0	0				0	0
	B.1.177 ^c	12	38	12	43			24	40
	B.1.1.7	0	0	0	0			0	0
	B.1.351	0	0	0	0			0	0
	P.1	0	0	0	0			0	0
Other lineages ^d	20	63	16	57			36	60	
1 Jan – 31 Jan 2021 ^e	Total SARS-CoV-2	9		8		535		552	
	Total sequenced	1	NC	5	NC	44	8	50	9
	B.1 ^b	0	NC	0	NC	1	2	1	2
	B.1.177 ^c	1	NC	4	NC	12	27	17	34
	B.1.1.7	0	NC	1	NC	26	59	27	54
	B.1.351	0	NC	0	NC	0	0	0	0
	P.1	0	NC	0	NC	0	0	0	0
Other lineages ^d	0	NC	0	NC	5	11	5	10	

NC = non-calculated (denominator is too small for meaningful percentages); NA = Not available

^a Among countries sequencing during the relevant time period.

^b Not including sub-lineages

^c Including B.1.177 and B.1.177.21

^d Other lineages include A, A.15, B.1.1, B1.11, B.1.1.117, B.1.1.130, B.1.1.170, B.1.1.198, B.1.1.26, B.1.1.261, B.1.1.294, B.1.1.302, B.1.1.304, B.1.1.313, B.1.1.64, B.1.1.90, B.1.1.91, B.1.146, B.1.160, B.1.221, B.1.258, B.1.36, B.1.428, B.1.88, B.11, B.3, B.1.1.74, B.1.1.75

^e Last sequencing date for Sweden 13 January 2021

3. Background

The end of 2019 saw the emergence of a novel severe acute respiratory syndrome – coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), which causes coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). The I-MOVE-COVID-19 consortium aims to obtain epidemiological and clinical information on patients with COVID-19 as well as virological information on SARS-CoV-2, through different work packages (WP):

- a) provision of a flexible surveillance platform, adaptable to the epidemiological situation, through WP2 (primary care surveillance) and WP3 (hospital surveillance)
- b) research studies, through WP4, and
- c) evaluation of public health interventions (e.g. vaccination, antivirals) in WP2–4

in order to contribute to the knowledge base, guide patient management, and inform the public health response. This is being achieved through adaptation and expansion of the existing I-MOVE network to include COVID-19. The network includes primary care networks, hospitals, and national laboratory reference centres in 10 countries across the WHO European Region.¹

The WP2 primary care surveillance for COVID-19 is coordinated by Nivel (Netherlands institute for health services research). The I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care network comprises nine sentinel surveillance networks in six European Union (EU) Member States (MS)² and in England and Scotland. The laboratory component of the network includes regional and national reference centres from the participating countries. While each of the surveillance sites analyses their data separately, pooling the data for overall analysis will provide a sample size big enough to answer study questions with reasonable precision.

The I-MOVE-COVID-19 consortium, coordinated by Epiconcept, was created following the European Commission's Call for Proposals H2020 "Advancing Knowledge for the Clinical and Public Health Response to the Emerging Coronavirus Epidemic". It brings together many partners already involved in the [I-MOVE](#) (Influenza - Monitoring Vaccine Effectiveness in Europe) network. I-MOVE, first established in 2007, was the first network to monitor influenza vaccine effectiveness (VE) within and across the seasons in the European Union (EU) and the European Economic Area (EEA). The network has two components, one for primary care practices, recruiting patients with influenza-like illness (ILI) and the other for hospitals, recruiting patients with severe acute respiratory illness (SARI). In February 2020, I-MOVE partners came together as the I-MOVE-COVID-19 consortium, and were successful in a bid for the H2020 call on "Advancing knowledge for the clinical and public health response to the novel coronavirus epidemic".

In this second surveillance report of COVID-19 in primary care, results are presented from participating primary care COVID-19 surveillance networks up to the end of January 2021. The results add to the ECDC surveillance data collection through TESSy (NCOVAGGR) and reporting

¹ Albania, France, Lithuania, Portugal, Romania, Spain, and the UK (England and Scotland).

² France, Ireland, The Netherlands, Portugal, Spain (two sites: the Spanish national system and the Navarra regional system) and Sweden.

(<https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/covid-19/surveillance/weekly-surveillance-report>) by providing more detailed information of COVID-19 cases in primary care.

More details on the data collection for I-MOVE-COVID-19 primary care surveillance can be found in the Generic Protocol.³ Briefly, the I-MOVE network is nested in sentinel practices carrying out surveillance for influenza and now COVID-19. Data is being collected from community-dwelling individuals who consult a participating physician with symptoms of suspected COVID-19. From all or from a systematic sample of suspected COVID-19 cases, primary care practitioners collect respiratory specimens as well as information on patient characteristics, and if possible, also on symptoms and potential risk factors and preventive factors for COVID-19. We refer to lab-confirmed SARS-CoV-2 COVID-19 patients as 'COVID-19 cases'. Participating primary care networks have implemented the generic protocol in their surveillance setting.

³ <https://www.imoveflu.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/D2.3-I-MOVE-COVID-19-Phased-surveillance-protocol.pdf>